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SCHOOL SEX-TYPE AND GENDER AS DETERMINANTS OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG J.S.S.3 STUDENTS IN CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

The study was carried out to ascertain the effects of school sex-type and gender on academic performance of J.S.S.3 students in Cross River State, Nigeria. School sex-type particularly classifies the schools according to the sex of the students attending those schools. The stratified random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 1600 J.S.S.3 students for the study. Out of this number, Seven hundred and Seventy-nine were males (48.7%) while the females were Eight hundred and twenty-one (51.3%). The ex-post facto research design was adopted. The data used were the results of J.S.S.3 students obtained from the Examinations and Certificate department of Ministry of Education, Cross River State. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and independent t-test. Findings revealed no significant differences in the mean scores of male and female students. There was no significant difference between the education quality received by male and female students based on their performance in the core subjects; yet significant difference was found in the mean scores of students from mixed (co-educational) schools and single-sexed schools. It was therefore, concluded that, national development cannot be achieved without qualitative education of the Nigerian citizens, especially the youths (which include J.S.S.3 students). For a balanced development, children of both sexes should be given equal opportunity of qualitative education without discrimination, while sending learners to mixed schools is advocated and highly encouraged. Recommendations were made.

Keywords: Education, Gender, School Sex-Type, Academic Performance and J.S.S.3 students.

Introduction

It is a generally accepted notion that, education is an instrument for national development. To this end, the formulation of ideas, their integration for national development and the interaction of persons and ideas are all aspects of education. Education—whether formal or informal is supposed to inculcate the right values and attitudes into individuals to enable them become well-adjusted and integrated members of their family first and then the wider society.

For a scholar like Obinaju(2012), education is seen as a deliberate and conscious attempt by the society using the medium of schools or institutions to familiarize the young with the values and beliefs of that particular society. Again, Rahuman and Uddin (2009) considered

education as one of the fundamental basic needs necessary for growth and development of nations – both developing and developed countries. Consequently, the education sector is pivotal to the actualization of our national goals and government policies.

A careful study of the trends of events around the world has shown that education for national development could be achieved through diverse strategies such as; Education for All, Gender Equality, Quality Education among others. At the world education forum(2000), six key goals of Education for All (EFA) were identified to include:

- Expanding early childhood care and education,
- Providing free and compulsory primary education for all,

- Promoting learning and life skills for young people and adults,
- Increasing adult literacy by 50%,
- Achieving gender parity by 2005 and gender equality by 2015, and
- Improving the quality of education.

Furthermore, UNESCO (2015) stated that, to achieve all the above EFA goals, both gender (male and female) must be exposed to quality education and be given equal opportunities in all areas of life.

In Nigeria today, the 9-3-4 system of education is operational and effective throughout the federation. The junior secondary school three (J.S.S.3) constitutes the last class of the upper basic level of the first stage of this unique system. Education especially at the J.S.S.3 level is regarded as the essential input of economic and national development of any nation (Kelly, Hewett, Mensch & Soler-Hampejsek, 2001).

Stressing the importance of education at this level, the national policy on Education (FRN, 2014) specifically stated that, the junior secondary education (J.S.S.1-3) shall achieve the following:

- Provide all primary school leavers with the opportunity for education of a higher level irrespective of sex, social status, religion or ethnic background.
- Offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities and future roles
- Inspire students with the desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence.

At the junior secondary school level, there are subjects that are considered as core subjects, they include: Mathematics, English Language, Basic Sciences, Social Studies, Agricultural Science, French or Language Arts. Indeed, the junior secondary level is the stage where students ought to make meaning of core subjects like Mathematics; its usefulness to life and application to further studies. It is the stage where decision to pursue mathematics related subjects and career in the future is made

(Uwaezuoke & Charles – Ogan, 2016). Admittedly, it is important at this level to provide qualitative education for every citizen, regardless of the gender, to ensure a balanced and healthy society, and as well secure a stable, meaningful life and well-being of the citizens of the nation.

In any given society where there are youngsters that would be educated to take over the society from the older generation, one would normally find male and female individuals eager to be trained. In the past, many societies and communities discriminated against the education of their female children, hence the adage “women education ends in the kitchen”. The belief then was that, the girls were transitory members of their families, and so, female education was unnecessary and useless to their birth homes (Ali, Adekeye & Raheem, 2011 and Osuuyikanmi, 2000). Thank goodness, as contemporary researches have shown that female education is quite beneficial to any society, nation and invariably the world (Kelly, 2013; UNESCO, 2013; Ekwueme, Ekon & Ezenwa-Nebife, 2016 and Idyorough, 2010)

School sex-type particularly classifies the schools (attended by the learners) according to the sex of the students in those schools. Some schools are mixed (co-educational) while others are single-sexed schools (either boys only or girls only). The school setting, either co-educational or single-sexed is very important. Learners of all ages and gender are enrolled into the various schools for effective teaching and learning, according to the school sex-type. Much research has been carried out in this regard. However, there is inherent controversy on whether co-educational schools are better or otherwise, compared to single-sexed schools.

For instance, Bela (1997) from his study found out that, school sex-type does not significantly influence students' achievement in science related subjects. Also, a study was conducted by Opie, Ovat & Meremikwu (2014) on school variables on Mathematics performance in Nigeria. One of the results of their analyses showed that, school sex-type significantly

influenced students' performance in Mathematics related subjects. In the same vein, Meremikwu, Igiri, Opie & Enuokoha (2012) reported from their study that, there was no significant difference in Mathematics performance between male and female students in mixed schools.

On the contrary, Mburu(2013), after his investigation stated that, there exist a significant difference in students' performance based on their school sex-type. Further analysis revealed that, boys in single-sexed schools performed significantly better than (had better grades) boys in mixed schools. Also, girls in single-sexed schools performed significantly better than their counterparts in mixed schools. To this end, school sex-type is an important factor to be reckoned with when considering the academic performance of students, especially J.S.S.3 students in the core subjects.

Interestingly, several studies have been undertaken in the field of educational psychology on the influence of sex on learners' academic performance. Cooley (2001) for instance, conducted a study on gender difference. The results of the study revealed that, there was no significant difference between the achievements of male and female students in science subjects, especially, at the age of nine years. The report of a work by Meremikwu (2008) stated that, the difference in academic ability of male and female learners is only noticeable depending on the influence of the school environment. The researcher further concluded that, between primary school and junior secondary school, gender sensitivity and difference do not exist, and that gender does not significantly influence learners' performance in a subject like Mathematics.

Conversely, Wigfield and Eccles (1994) reported from their study that, female students performed better than the male students in English Language, Mathematics, Sciences and Social studies. Furthermore, Uguma (2013) assessed the influence of gender on the achievement level of Senior Secondary School (S.S.2) students in English Language. The outcome of the study was quite interesting. The results of the analysis showed that, in urban

centers, female students performed significantly better than their female counterparts in rural areas. The same scenario was witnessed in the rural schools where the female students performed significantly better than their male counterparts.

From the foregoing review, it is evident that, gender significantly affects students' performance in some subjects. While in some, gender discrimination may not be significant at the junior level, but become powerful at the higher level as the students mature.

Sometime ago, Ekwueme et al (2016) had posited that, gender equality through sustainable development implies giving every boy or girl, man or woman equal opportunity to obtain quality education. But UNESCO (2013) reported that, 35 million girls of primary school age were out of school while 37 million girls of junior secondary school age were also out of school. This is an aberration that prompted this study. The setting in Cross River State is unique. Culturally, equal opportunities are accorded to both male and female children. In such an environment where equal educational opportunity, learning environment and all that would enhance academic achievement are provided for the students irrespective of their sexes; the researchers curiously wonder whether there is any difference between male and female students' education quality with regards to their performance in the core subjects.

Therefore, the study sets out to ascertain the effects of school sex-type and gender on academic performance of junior secondary school (J.S.S.3) students in Nigeria; Cross River State as a case study.

Purpose of study: Specifically, this study aimed at determining;

1. Whether school sex-type do influence J.S.S.3 students' academic performance in the core subjects.
2. Whether there exists any difference between the academic performance of male and female J.S.S.3 students' in the core subjects.

Research questions:

- To what extent does school sex-type influence the J.S.S.3 students' education quality and their academic performance in the core subjects?
- What is the difference between male and female J.S.S.3 students' education quality based on their academic performance in the core subjects?

Statements of hypotheses:

1. There is no significant influence of school sex type on J.S.S.3 students' academic performance in the core subjects.
2. There is no significant difference between J.S.S.3 male and female students based on their academic performance in the core subjects.

Methodology:

The study focused on junior secondary school (J.S.S.3) students in schools spread across the 18 Local Government Areas of Cross River State. The schools under study

included single-sexed schools (boys only and girls only) as well as mixed schools.

The study population comprised 31,885 J.S.S.3 students registered in the target area. This number consisted of male and female students. These J.S.S.3 students registered and wrote the 2016 J.S.S examination, in the different education zones of the study area. The stratified random sampling technique was used to randomly select a sample of 1600 J.S.S. students for the study. Out of this number, seven hundred and seventy-nine were males (48.7%) while the females were eight hundred and twenty-one (51.3%). Being a systematic empirical inquiry; the study adopted the ex-post facto research design. The data was majorly the results (academic performance) of J.S.S.3 students from the Examination and Certificate department of Ministry of Education, Cross River State. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics, independent t-test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

Results

Table 1 shows the results of descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) of J.S.S.3 students in some core subjects based on their school sex-type. And school sex-type was categorized into mixed, all-boys and all-girls schools. The actual results of ANOVA are shown in table 2.

TABLE 1
Means and Standard deviations of J.S.S.3 students' performances in the core subjects based on School Sex-type.

Core Subjects	Group (School sex-type)	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D
English Language	1 (Mixed)	1341	63.42	10.6
	2 (All boys)	99	64.72	11.05
	3 (All girls)	160	64.16	7.57
	Total	1600	63.58	10.37
Mathematics	1 (Mixed)	1341	56.46	12.94
	2 (All boys)	99	54.04	9.84
	3 (All girls)	160	58.53	13.65
	Total	1600	56.51	12.87
Social Studies	1 (Mixed)	1341	68.88	11.62
	2 (All boys)	99	74.81	10.52
	3 (All girls)	160	69.48	9.84
	Total	1600	69.3	11.47

The results in table 1 showed that, the sizes, means and standard deviations of the three groups of students (based on school sex-type) concerning the J.S.S.3 students' academic performance in the core subjects under consideration.

Hypothesis one:

There is no significant influence of school sex-type on J.S.S.3 students' academic performance in the core subjects.

TABLE 2
One-way analysis of variance of the influence of school sex-type on J.S.S.3 students' academic performance in the core subjects.

Core Subjects	Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	F-Value
English Language	Between Groups	216.35	2	108.18	1.01
	Within Groups	171658.65	1597	107.49	
	Total	171875	1599		
Mathematics	Between Groups	1261.23	2	630.62	3.822*
	Within Groups	263352.17	1597	165.01	
	Total	210382.68	1599		
Social Studies	Between Groups	3248.7	2	1624.35	12.52*
	Within Groups	207133.98	1597	129.78	
	Total	210382.68	1599		

*Significant at 0.5 level; critical $F=2.99(\alpha.05, d.f=2, 1597)$

TABLE 3
Fisher's LSD post-hoc analysis of J.S.S.3 students' performance based on school sex type

Subject	Groups	Mixed(N=13)		
		41	Boys(N=99)	Girls(N=160)
Mathematics	1 (Mixed)	56.46□	2.42□	-2.07
	2 (All Boys)	1.81□	54.04	-4.49
	3 (All Girls)	-1.93	-2.73*	58.53
		MSw=165.01		
Social Studies	1 (Mixed)	68.88□	-5.93□	-0.6
	2 (All Boys)	-5.00□	74.81	5.33
	3 (All Girls)	-0.63	3.66*	69.48
		MSw=148.73		

Note: a – Group means are placed along the diagonal
 b–Difference in group means are above the diagonal
 c –Fisher's t-values are the placed below the diagonal
 *Significant at 0.5 level, critical $t=1.96$

The actual results of ANOVA presented in table 2 showed that, the calculated F-values for Mathematics (3.822) and Social Studies (12.52) were each greater than the critical F-value of 2.99 at .05 level of significance with 2 and 1597 degrees of freedom. With these results, the null hypothesis is rejected for the two subjects (Mathematics and Social Studies). However, the calculated F-value of 1.01 for

English language was observed to be lower than the critical F-value of 2.99. This leads to the retention of the null hypothesis. Thus, the F-value indicated that there was a significant influence of school sex-type on the education quality of J.S.S.3 students based on their academic performance in mathematics and social studies, but not in English language.

Hypothesis two:

There is no significant difference between the male and female J.S.S.3 students based on their performance in the core subjects. Table 4

shows the results of the independent t-test analysis of the male and female J.S.S.3 students' performances in the core subjects considered.

TABLE 4
Independent t-test of differences between male and female J.S.S.3 students' academic performances in the core subjects.

Core Subjects	Groups	N	$\bar{X}$	S.D	t-value
English Language	1 (Male)	779	63.25	10.79	-1.21
	2 (Female)	821	63.88	9.95	
Mathematics	1 (Male)	779	56.28	12.24	-0.71
	2 (Female)	821	56.74	13.44	
Social Studies	1 (Male)	779	69.54	11.62	0.80
	2 (Female)	821	69.08	11.33	

*t-value is significant at .05 level; critical $t = 1.96(\alpha.05, d.f = 1598)$

The results presented in the table above indicated that, the calculated t-values of -1.21 (for English language), -0.71 (for Mathematics) and 0.80 (for Social Studies) were each lower than the critical value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance with 1598 degrees of freedom. With these results the null hypothesis (hypothesis two) is not rejected for any of the 3 core subjects under consideration. This implies that, the male students were not significantly different from the female students based on their performances in English language, Mathematics and Social Studies. As such gender does not significantly determine the education quality and the academic performance of J.S.S.3 students whether male or female.

Discussion of results:

For English language: students in all-boys schools ($\bar{X}=64.72$ and $S.D=11.05$) performed significantly higher than students in all-girls schools (with $\bar{X}=64.16$ and $S.D=7.57$). However, the academic performance of students in mixed schools (with $\bar{X}=63.42$ and $S.D=10.6$) was not significantly better than the performance of those students in all-boys schools and the performance of those in all-girls schools.

For Mathematics: The performance of students in all-girls schools (with $\bar{X}=58.53$ and $S.D=13.65$) was significantly higher than those of students in all-boys schools (with $\bar{X}=54.04$ and $S.D=9.84$). Interestingly, students in mixed schools (with $\bar{X}=56.46$ and $S.D=12.94$) performed significantly better than students in allboys schools, but their performance was not better than that of students in allgirls schools.

For Social studies: The performance of students in all-boys schools (with $\bar{X}=74.81$ and $S.D 10.52$) was significantly higher than those of students from allgirls schools (with $\bar{X}=69.48$ and $S.D=9.84$). Notwithstanding, the performance of students in mixed schools (with $\bar{X}=68.88$ and $S.D=11.62$) was not significantly better than the performance of students from both all-girls and allboys school.

The ANOVA results of hypothesis one showed that, there was a significant influence of school sex-type on the education quality of J.S.S.3 students based on their performances in subjects like Mathematics and Social Studies. Notwithstanding, there was no significant influence of school sex-type on the students' performance in English language. Indeed mixed (co-educational) schools did not show gender sensitivity in the J.S.S.3 students' performance in the core subjects like

mathematics. However, gender sensitivity was significant in single-sexed schools. In such schools, the performance of boys in core subjects like Social Studies was higher than those of the girls in single-sexed schools (all girls) schools; also, girls did not perform better in Mathematics in single-sexed schools (girls only) than their male counterparts in single-sexed (all boys) schools.

Again, the independent t-test results of hypothesis two showed that, there was no significant difference between the male and female J.S.S.3 students based on their performances in the three core subjects (English, Mathematics and Social Studies). Thus the results of the analyses showed that gender is not a significant factor when considering factors influencing students' academic performance among J.S.S.3 students in Cross River State. This result is in agreement with the work of Okoye (1987), who stated that, even though the biological properties between males and females are different, notwithstanding gender sensitivity on students' academic performance among junior secondary school students are not pronounced among Nigerian students. Collaborating Meremikwu (2008) found out from her work that, gender sensitivity was not a significant factor for Mathematics achievement among junior secondary school students in the Calabar education zone of Cross River State.

In spite of the preceding research findings, an analysis of the data with respect to school sex-type showed that, school sex-type significantly influenced J.S.S.3 students' performance in Mathematics and Social Studies only. The Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) of table 3 indicated that, for Mathematics, boys in single-sexed (boys only) schools performed significantly higher than girls in single-sexed (girls only) schools. On the contrary, there was no significant difference in their performance in Mathematics in mixed (co-educational) schools. The implication is that, to remove gender sensitivity between girls and boys in a subject like Mathematics they should be allowed to compete with each other in mixed

schools. Mixed schools create a forum for students' interaction; such interactions help the students to learn better and from each other. The resultant effect of this competitive spirit is that, students strive to achieve better than their counterparts.

On the overall, this study collaborating Opie, Ovat & Meremikwu (2014) discovered that, school sex-type significantly influenced students' performance in some core subjects, especially Mathematics ($F=3.22$, $p<.05$) and Social Studies ($F=12.52$; $p<.05$). Furthermore, Mburu (2013) reported that, students in single-sexed secondary schools have advantages over their counterparts in mixed schools. Yet the present study has showed that, there was no significant difference in academic performance between students in mixed schools and single-sexed (all boys or all girls) schools especially in Mathematics. Clearly, it is seen that gender sensitivity in academic performance is evidenced in single-sexed schools; and given the opportunity, female students in single-sexed school can compete favourably with their male counterparts in single-sexed (all male) schools.

Contribution to knowledge:

Evidently, the study has revealed that, school sex-type significantly influenced the J.S.S.3 students' performance in the core subjects. And that, there was no significant difference in the qualitative education received by male and female J.S.S.3 students based on their performance in the core subjects considered. Gender does not determine the academic performance of the J.S.S.3 students. These would provide further literature for researchers in future.

Implications for national development:

The present study considered peculiarities such as: the learners (male and female J.S.S.3 students), taught with the same curriculum contents, the various teaching methods (processes) were used, they wrote the same statewide standardized J.S.S.3 examinations the same year and their academic performances (outcomes) were obtained from the Cross River

State Ministry of Education. The study unveils some interesting implications:

- National development cannot be well achieved without the training of the Nigerian citizens, especially the youths – part of who are the J.S.S.3 students in secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria.
- For a balanced development in our nation, children of both sexes (male and female) should be given equal opportunity of qualitative education without discrimination.
- Educating children in mixed (co-educational) schools should be encouraged. This creates a forum for students' interactions, allows for competition among the students, as well as, learning better and from each other.
- Availability of quality education for children of both sexes in co-educational schools with the beneficial students' interactions would psychologically empower the learners and inspire them to be responsible citizens actively living with sustainable consciousness.
- In line with one of the goals of junior secondary school education; this level of education would improve the quality of life, educational attainment of this category of citizens, achievement of excellence as well as the chances for economic and social wellbeing of the next generation.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings and implications of this study:

- 1) Government at local, state and federal levels should build more mixed (co-educational) schools especially for learners at the junior secondary school level.
- 2) Parents should be encouraged to send their children at the early stage of their education to mixed schools for academic and social interactions.
- 3) Since there is no significant difference in the education quality of male and

female students, guidance and counseling experts advised on the reduction or a halt in the establishment of single-sexed schools.

- 4) Both genders should be exposed and given equal opportunities in all areas of their lives and learning.
- 5) Parents and communities should be periodically enlightened afresh by counselors to see the need to give both male and female children of every family, equal opportunity of qualitative education up to the upper basic level (J.S.S) and beyond. The resultant effect would be a comprehensive and balanced national development.

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